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4. Performance of Tourism Industry in India – Issues, Challenges and Growth

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Introduction

India is one of the major democratic nations of the world. It has achieved considerable progress after initiation of reforms in 1991. It has emerged as the fourth largest economy in purchasing power and it is amongst the fastest growing nations in the world. It has made great advances in many fields particularly Information Technology (IT). With a large pool of educated English speaking citizens, India has emerged as an important outsourcing destination for many multi-national companies. It has launched its own satellites and sent a spacecraft to moon. Thus, India is booming in recent years. India stands out for the size and dynamism of its services sector. Thus, one of the striking aspects of India's recent growth has been the dynamism of the services, particularly IT and ITES (IT enabled services). The medical tourism industry is poised to be the next big success story in India after IT (software).

In over a decade time, distinguishable growth of tourism has resulted its emergence as an important sector of the Indian economy with considerable contribution in terms of foreign exchange, income and employment opportunities. Many factors can be seen as responsible for this and some major ones in the process have been increase in the volume of tourist flow, increase in the proportion of high spending tourists, accelerated spread in the volume of tourists geographically, pro-active government policies and growing interest from investors. Appreciable growth in all three forms of tourism- domestic, outbound and inbound have been demonstratively catalytic in their role as agents of positive contribution in the socio-economic development in the country.

Performance of Tourism Industry

Tourism is one of the major components of India's services and engines of growth, contributing around 6.11 percent of GDP and 10 percent of employment. This sector is estimated to create 78 jobs per million Indian rupees of investment compared to 45 jobs per million rupees in the manufacturing sector (Planning Commission, 2011). The annual growth of this sector is estimated to be 8.1 percent during the last five years. Performance indicators of this industry that are shown in the Table, Foreign Tourist Arrivals (FTAs) from the year 2000 to 2013 and percentage share and rank of India in world and percentage share and rank of India in Asia and the Pacific.

**Share of India in International Tourist Arrivals in World and Asia & the Pacific Region
2000 - 2013**

Year	International Tourist Arrivals (in million)		FTAs in India (in Million)	Percentage share and rank of India in World		Percentage share and rank of India in Asia and the Pacific	
	World	Asia and the Pacific		percentage Share	Rank	percentage Share	Rank
2000	683.3	109.3	2.65	0.39	50 th	2.42	11 th
2001	683.4	114.5	2.54	0.37	51 st	2.22	12 th
2002	703.2	123.4	2.38	0.34	54 th	1.93	12 th
2003	691.0	111.9	2.73	0.39	51 st	2.44	11 th
2004	762.0	143.4	3.46	0.45	44 th	2.41	11 th
2005	803.4	154.6	3.92	0.49	43 rd	2.53	11 th
2006	846.0	166.0	4.45	0.53	44 th	2.68	11 th
2007	894.0	182.0	5.08	0.57	41 st	2.79	11 th
2008	917.0	184.1	5.28	0.58	41 st	2.87	11 th
2009	883.0	181.1	5.17	0.59	41 st	2.85	11 th
2010	948.0	204.9	5.78	0.61	42 nd	2.82	11 th
2011	995.0	218.5	6.31	0.63	38 th	2.89	9 th
2012	1035.0	233.5	6.58	0.64	41 st	2.82	11 th
2013	1087.0 (P)	248.1(P)	6.97	0.64	42 nd	2.81	11 th

P: Provisional,

(iv) UNWTO Barometer April 2014 for 2010, 2011, 2012 & 2013

Source:-(i) UNWTO Tourism Market Trends 2007 Edition, for the years upto 2005.

(ii) UNWTO Barometer June 2010 for 2006 and January 2011 for 2007

(iii) UNWTO Tourism Highlights 2011 Edition for 2008 and 2012 Edition for 2009.

(iv) UNWTO Barometer April 2014 for 2010, 2011, 2012 & 2013

In India, tourism industry identified as one of the five T's (Tradition, Talent, Tourism, Trade and Technology) for revival of 'Brand India'. It recognizes the role of tourism and hospitality as a key foreign exchange earner as well as a driver of socio-economic progress through creation of jobs, enterprise, infrastructure development and foreign exchange earnings. Government plans to create 50 tourist circuits built around various themes. It also plans to create a specialized plan for capacity development in tourism and to focus on safety and security of tourists.

Key Issues/Challenges of Indian Tourism Industry

- **Skilled manpower:** Forecasted requirement of around 2.8 million employees for restaurants, 4.1 million employees for hotels and 0.3 million employees for the travel trade segment by 2022 resulting in an additional requirement of 2.7 million employees for the tourism sector, as compared to 2012 employment figures (NSDC study)
- **Poor infrastructure:** There is significant potential to improve transport, road as well as hotel infrastructure which will have a direct bearing on the tourism sector

- **Inadequate safety and security of tourists:** India ranks 74 amongst 140 global economies on safety and security parameters as per the World Economic Forum's T&T Competitiveness Report 2013. There is a severe need to improve the country's ranking.

Below table shows the share of top 10 countries of the world and India in International tourism receipts in the year 2013. Among the top 10 countries USA occupies first position in international tourism followed by Spain, France, China, China, Italy, Thailand, Germany, UK, and China. The top 10 countries share was about 48.83 percent. India's share was only 1.59 percent and rest of the countries share was about 49.58 percent. Hence India needs to make more efforts to increase the share with other nations.

Share of Top 10 Countries of the World and India in International Tourism Receipts in 2013

Rank	Country	International Tourist Receipts (P) (in US \$ billion)	Percentage Share
1.	USA	139.6	12.04
2.	Spain	60.4	5.21
3.	France	56.1	4.84
4.	China	51.7	4.46
5.	Macao (China)	51.6	4.45
6.	Italy	43.9	3.79
7.	Thailand	42.1	3.63
8.	Germany	41.2	3.55
9.	United Kingdom	40.6	3.50
10.	Hong Kong(China)	38.9	3.36
Total of Top 10 Countries		566.1	48.83
	India	18.4	1.59
	Others	574.5	49.58
	Total	1159.0	100.00

P: Provisional.

Source: UNWTO Barometer April 2014 and Ministry of Tourism (MOT).

Future of the Tourism Industry

The industry had high expectations from budget 2014-2015. The key pre-budget recommendations for this sector included the following

- ✓ Prioritisation of key issues such as safety and infrastructure
- ✓ Swift implementation of electronic travel authorization and e-Visa
- ✓ Infrastructure enhancement
- ✓ Rationalisation of taxes
- ✓ Grant of export industry status.

The country was expecting a budget that puts the economy back on track and restores investor confidence. With the challenge of limited fiscal space for bringing in the tax reforms, the Finance Minister announced the following key budget proposals.

Key announcements by Government of India

- ✓ **Central Plan outlay:** Increased to INR1,507 crore from INR980 crore
- ✓ **e-Visa:** To be introduced in a phased manner at nine airports in the next six months
- ✓ **Tourist circuits:** Allocated INR500 crore for developing five tourist circuits
- ✓ **National Mission on Pilgrimage Rejuvenation and Spiritual Augmentation Drive (PRASAD):** Allocated INR100 crore
- ✓ **North-east rail connectivity:** Allocated INR1,000 crore (over and above interim budget allocation)
- ✓ **Convention centre at Goa:** Assistance through VGF (Viability Gap Funding) for a convention centre in Goa to be implemented through PPPs
- ✓ **Heritage cities:** Allocated INR200 crore for preserving heritage character of Mathura, Amritsar, Gaya, Kanchipuram, Vellankani and Ajmer
- ✓ **Exemption of service tax** for Indian tour operators arranging tours wholly outside the country for foreigners
- ✓ **CENVAT credit to tour operators:** Credit for services of rent-a-cab and tour operators
- ✓ **Adventure tourism:** An annual event to promote unique Himalayan region sports to be held
- ✓ **REITs:** Incentives and pass-through status for taxation of REITs
- ✓ **Airports:** To be developed in Tier-2 and Tier-3 cities.

With multiple announcements which directly/indirectly impact the sector, the budget is encouraging for the tourism sector and a step in the right direction.

Policy impact

The time bound directive for implementation of the e-Visa scheme at nine airports is expected to increase inbound visitor flow substantially. This is particularly expected to impact the business and Meeting Incentive Conference and Exhibition segment (MICE) segments. In addition, proposed investments in transport infrastructure such as modernization of railways, development of new airports and significant focus on road connectivity augurs well for the sector. Substantial fund allocation to the North East for improving rail connectivity is likely to enhance tourism in one of the most under-tapped tourist destinations in India. Some of the other initiatives are preserving heritage cities and development of five circuits with reasonable fund allocation gives an indication of a focused approach for developing tourism. The proposal of 'Namami Ganga' is also expected to give a boost to tourism. These along with other policy announcements regarding increased FDI in several sectors and clarity on setting up of REITs, are catalysts for growth.

Overseas Offices and its Marketing objectives

The Ministry of Tourism, Government of India, through its 14 offices overseas endeavors to position India in the tourism generating markets as a preferred tourism destination, to promote various Indian tourism products vis-à-vis competition faced from various destinations and to increase India's share of the global tourism market.

The above objectives are met through an integrated marketing and promotional strategy and a synergized campaign in association with the Travel Trade, State Governments and Indian Missions. The specific elements of promotions efforts undertaken overseas include Advertising in the Print & Electronic Media, Participation in Fairs & Exhibitions, Organizing Seminars, Workshops, Road Shows & India Evenings, Printing of Brochures and Collaterals, Brochure Support/Joint Advertising with Travel Agents / Tour Operators, Inviting the Media and Travel Trade to visit the country under the Hospitality Programme etc.

Government of India has launched Tourist Visa on Arrival (TVoA) enabled by Electronic Travel Authorization on 27th November 2014 for 43 countries. Prior to it, the normal TVoA scheme used to operate for 12 countries. The following are the important highlights of VoAs issued during November, 2014.

- During the month of November 2014, a total of 2,968 VoAs were issued under this Scheme as compared to 1,824 VoAs during the month of November 2013, registering a growth of 62.7%.
- During January- November 2014, a total number of 24,963 VoAs were issued as compared to 17,594 VoAs during corresponding period of 2013 registering a growth of 41.9%.
- The number of VoAs issued under this scheme during November 2014 for nationals of the twelve countries were South Korea (837), Singapore (467), New Zealand (427), the Philippines (350), Indonesia (326), Japan (310), Finland (125), Myanmar (64), Vietnam (22), Cambodia (20), Luxembourg (18) and Laos (2) .
- The number of VoAs issued under the Scheme, during January- November 2014 were South Korea (5,080), Japan (4,683), New Zealand (3,690), Singapore (3,494), the Philippines (3,346), Indonesia (2,776), Finland (990), Myanmar (391), Vietnam (238), Cambodia (129), Luxembourg (126) and Laos (20).
- During January- November 2014, the highest number of VoAs were issued at New Delhi airport (11,579) followed by Mumbai (4,897), Chennai (3,512), Bangalore (1,698), Kolkata (1,600), Kochi (839), Hyderabad (600) and Trivandrum (238).

Below chart shows number of visa's issued under the scheme of VoA during January 2014 to November 2014. Among the various countries 5080 tourist visa are issued to people visited from South Korea followed by 4683 visitor from Japan, 3690 visitor from New Zealand, 3494 visitor from Singapore, 3346 visitor from Philippines, 2776 visitors from Indonesia, 990 visitors from Finland, 391 visitors from Myanmar, 238 visitors from Vietnam, 129 visitors from Cambodia, 126 visitors from Luxembourg and 20 visitors from Loas are benefited.

Source: Bureau of Immigration, Govt. of India

Use of Incredible India logo and capacity building

The Incredible India brand is one of the most recognized brands internationally. The Ministry of Tourism would give permission for the use of Incredible India logo for the wellness and medical tourism promotion events, films, literature etc., as per the prescribed procedure from time to time. Trained human resource is an important component of any tourism product, including Wellness & Medical Tourism. A large number of tourism service providers in the organized/unorganized sector require basic and advanced training in related areas to provide better service standards and consumer satisfaction. The Ministry of Tourism would provide financial support for training courses focussed on skill providing, skill up-gradation and skill certification courses for the persons engaged in Wellness & Medical Tourism sector as per the Capacity Building for Service Providers (CBSP) scheme guidelines of the Ministry of Tourism. The training could be at various levels, i.e., basic level, higher level, advanced level and specialized. The Ministry of Tourism would provide space up to 4 Square Meters to Wellness and / or Medical Tourism Associations at major international fairs for promoting Wellness and Medical Tourism at cost.

Major Problems of Tourists in India

Domestic tourists

- i. Bad conditions of roads and highway, unhygienic destinations, higher room rates, inadequate infrastructure at transport modes emerged as most rated concerns.
- ii. Other issues worth noting are tourism/ cheating, badly managed attraction sites, improper behavior of some section of service providers and the public.

- iii. Higher domestic airfares seem to be less concerning; a trend perhaps attributable to a very low proportion of domestic air transport users.

Foreign tourists

- i. Tourism / cheating, unhygienic destinations, inadequate infrastructure at transport modes and bad roads and highways.
- ii. They are also equally concerned about poor maintenance of tourist attraction sites, bad behavior of service providers like shopkeepers, taxi drivers as well as the general public.
- iii. Incidentally, higher domestic airfares.

Conclusion

The travel and tourism industry has emerged as one of the largest and fastest growing economic sectors globally and the industry's contribution to the global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and employment has increased significantly and it is emerging as an important category of services exports worldwide. And especially in India tourism industry provide more employment opportunity as well as contribute more on GDP. Now the Government of India takes various measures to attract the foreign tourist. So near future India can expect more growth in the tourism sector.

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